

SOCIAL SCIENCES

DEMOCRATIC "RITUALS" IN AUTHORITARIAN SOVIET GEORGIA

Giorgi Gogokhia,

Ph. D. candidate of Mass Communication Doctoral Educational Program

Caucasus International University

Chargali Str. 73, 0141, Tbilisi, Georgia

Khatuna Kacharava

Ph. D. in Journalism, Associate Professor

Caucasus International University

Abstract

This paper examines the role of elections in Soviet Georgia between 1921 and 1990. It argues that elections did not serve as a genuine democratic tool but instead acted as ritualistic displays of state power. The research explores how the Soviet regime legitimized its rule after occupying Georgia in 1921 and how, especially after the adoption of the 1936 Constitution, the electoral system was designed to create the illusion of democracy while in reality reinforcing one-party rule. Using historical records and Soviet press materials, the study shows that elections were marked by limited participation, preselected candidates, and symbolic mass involvement. The Georgian example reflects the broader Soviet strategy of disguising authoritarian rule with the appearance of democratic procedures.

Keywords: Soviet, Elections, Georgia, Party

Since 1917, a civil war had been taking place in Russia. This military and political condition did not allow the country to conduct firm foreign processes. On March 7, 1920, Russia signed a peace agreement with Georgia, according to which it recognized the country's independence and sovereignty. As in the previous historical and political relations between Russia and Georgia, the agreement was not binding for Russia during this period either, and in 1921 it took military steps. Along with other military decisions, the occupation of Georgia was important for Russia. "In February 1921, by order of Moscow, the Red Army entered the territory of Georgia, which was carried out in violation of the 1920 peace treaty against a sovereign country" (Andersen & Partskhaladze, 2009). The experience of independence and democracy of the First Republic of Georgia could not guarantee the prevention of occupation. The technical and numerical advantage of the Soviet army played a decisive role in the military action. Russia defeated the 11,000-man Georgian army with 40,000 soldiers, and the motive was presented as support for a local people's revolution. "The large-scale attack on Georgia was preceded by the so-called 'people's uprising' staged by the Soviet Union against the Georgian government, which was mainly carried out in the Borchalo region, inhabited predominantly by Armenians" (Andersen & Partskhaladze, 2009). This citation shows the situation in which the Soviet Union used political manipulation to legitimize its intervention. However, it is important to note that in reality, the Georgian population perceived the political reality negatively. After three years of independence, during which many democratic processes were carried out compared to the time, a new reality emerged, which people perceived as the loss of freedom and the legalization of Soviet rule by force (Clingerman, 2020).

"On March 17–18, 1921, an agreement was signed regarding the cessation of military actions. Russia finally conquered Georgia" (LIBERTY, 2023). The above-described political and military events led to Georgia becoming part of the Soviet Union, which continued until 1991. In Soviet Georgia, which was part of the Soviet Union, elections as a democratic form were not held. Based on the authoritarian reality of the USSR, the need for elections was not logically present. However, before 1936, we do find minor forms of electoral processes in the history of Georgia. The 1922 constitutional act of the United Soviet Republics defined the type of elections, in which only a class-restricted part of society participated. Peasants, workers, Red Army soldiers, and the "working" intelligentsia had the right to vote, while representatives of the bourgeoisie, religious institutions, and other groups did not. This approach resulted in a class-based electoral process which, by its content, was purely formal (White, 1982).

In periodicals of that time, such as „*Zaria Vostoka*“, prior to 1936, one frequently encounters information about the administrative aspects of elections, including the number of candidates, delegates, and participants. The journal provides insight into the structure of electoral processes, which were clearly non-democratic in nature. For instance, the October 1934 issue (No. 249) of „*Zaria Vostoka*“ describes how delegates referred to as "workers of the people" were to be selected for the Transcaucasian Soviet Congress. These delegates not only represented various Soviet institutions but also actively promoted party propaganda. The number of delegates was specified separately for Georgia, Adjara, South Ossetia, and Abkhazia (ZFENDIEV & TODRIYA, 1934). The selection of delegates was to occur at Soviet congresses, after which the results would be reported to

the public by the elected deputies. The elections were evidently formalistic, as citizens had no real choice. Furthermore, the November issue No. 268 of the same year notes that in several districts of Transcaucasia, elections were held for the purpose of delegate selection. The undemocratic nature of the process is evident even within the Soviet journal itself, which states: "Elections held with the participation of individuals deprived of their voting rights cannot be regarded as legitimate" („Правда“, 1934).

A new stage in the Soviet Union began in 1936, when its leader, Joseph Stalin, laid the foundation for a new constitution. The political environment of the Soviet Union reached the conclusion that "class enemies" were no longer a threat, and the Union was already ready for full democracy. At the 1934 Party Congress, with Stalin's great effort, the essence of the 1936 constitution was discussed. The goal of the constitution was to conduct democratic processes, particularly elections. Despite the stated goal, in all Soviet elections held from 1937 onwards, it became evident that the process reflected party ideology rather than democratic practice. The constitution and the electoral procedures it defined were a kind of political strategy strengthening power through the appearance of formal democratic institutions. "Soviet elections were a curtain hiding the totalitarian rule of a small group of people" (Фокин, 2014). Elections, as a process meant to connect with the equal population and as a response to Western criticism, were held in Georgia with great resonance. As in other Soviet republics, one-party elections were held in Georgia with the following characteristics:

- Election candidates were individuals selected by the party
- The majority of the population participated in the elections
- Not participating in elections was considered a dissident act

The media response and involvement in relation to the elections, alongside informing the population, was inherently propagandistic. The Soviet media agenda was constructed around the party narrative and focused on disseminating information that glorified the Soviet Union. As one article noted: "By casting their ballot for the candidates of the bloc of Communists and non-party members, the Soviet citizen is thereby voting for the prosperity of the homeland, for the improvement of the people's lives, and for the policies of the Lenin-Stalin Party." (Pravda, Zaria Vostoka, 1939). As mentioned above, popular participation was practically universal. Voters were compelled to take the one-party elections seriously and to take part in them. As reported: "The voters were eagerly fulfilling their civic duty. The high political engagement of Soviet citizens was once again confirmed." (Pravda, Zaria Vostoka, 1939).

In terms of evaluation, it can ultimately be said that elections during the Soviet era resembled a political ritual more than a democratic process. Although the 1936 Constitution proclaimed elections to be universal, equal, direct, and conducted by secret ballot, in reality, candidates were still selected by the

Party, and elections were typically held with only one candidate per district: "the Soviet Constitution of 1936 was adopted on the eve of the Great Terror of the late 1930s; the „thoroughly democratic“ elections to the first Supreme Soviet permitted only uncontested candidates and took place at the height of the savage violence in 1937." (Getty, 1991).

Bibliography

1. „Правда“. (1934, November 20). Zaria Vostoka N268. Retrieved from საქართველოს ეროვნული ბიბლიოთეკა: https://dSPACE.nplg.gov.ge/bitstream/1234/528491/1/Zaria_Vostoka_1934_N268.pdf
2. Andersen, A., & Partskhaladze, G. (2009). Soviet-Georgian War and Sovietization of Georgia, I-II. 1921. *Revue historique des Armées*, 4.
3. Clingerman, I. E. (2020). Analyzing the Georgian Opinion of the Soviet Annexation of Georgia. *Bucknell Digital Commons*, 15-20.
4. Getty, J. A. (1991). State and Society Under Stalin. *Constitutions and Elections in The 1930s. Slavic Review*, 18-20.
5. Jones, S. (2013). The establishment of Soviet power in Transcaucasia: The case of Georgia 1921–1928. *Soviet Studies*, 625.
6. LIBERTY, G. (2023). 1921. Retrieved from GEORGIAN LIBERTY: <https://www.georgianliberty.com/ge/1921>
7. Vostoka, Z. (1934, November 20). Zaria Vostoka. Retrieved from ეროვნული ბიბლიოთეკა: https://dSPACE.nplg.gov.ge/bitstream/1234/528491/1/Zaria_Vostoka_1934_N268.pdf
8. White, S. (1982). *Communist Legislatures in Comparative Perspective*. London : Palgrave Macmillan .
9. ZFENDIEV, M., & TODRIYA, S. (1934, October 26). Zaria Vostoka. Retrieved from ეროვნული ბიბლიოთეკა: https://dSPACE.nplg.gov.ge/bitstream/1234/528466/1/Zaria_Vostoka_1934_N249.pdf
10. Правда. (1939, December 26). Zaria Vostoka. Retrieved from ეროვნული ბიბლიოთეკა: https://dSPACE.nplg.gov.ge/bitstream/1234/468333/1/Zaria_Vostoka_1939_N297.pdf
11. Правда. (1939, December 26). Zaria Vostoka. Retrieved from ეროვნული ბიბლიოთეკა: https://dSPACE.nplg.gov.ge/bitstream/1234/468333/1/Zaria_Vostoka_1939_N297.pdf
12. Правда. (1939, December 26). Zaria Vostoka. Retrieved from ეროვნული ბიბლიოთეკა: https://dSPACE.nplg.gov.ge/bitstream/1234/468333/1/Zaria_Vostoka_1939_N297.pdf
13. Фокин, А. (2014). Выборы в СССР в 1960-1970е гг. *Soviet History Discussion Papers*, 1-2.